

Virtual Learning : Theatre in Education during COVID-19

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Abstract :

It is obvious that “corona virus disease (COVID-19)” is presently sweeping the world. As the academic institutions closed to prevent the spread of COVID-19, all the disciplines turned their approach from physical classroom to virtual. In case of theatre arts, the adaptation of virtual classroom has demonstrated exclusive challenges. This article examines the influence of COVID-19 in “theatre in education” asking following questions: What are the challenges encountered in virtual theatre classes in school education? What are the possible ways to resolve these challenges? How is a teacher finding alternative methods in taught curriculum? And how is the interaction between a teacher and students in these classes? To present this paper, the researcher identified themes of motivation, innovation and “online teaching”. The research is the evidences interpretations of various applications and methods for virtual learning.

Introduction :

The Spanish flu, in 1918, was reason to shut institutions of performing-arts around the world. Now, one can observe a similar kind of pandemic. It is obvious that these pandemics are hard times, but educators have found online teaching method in COVID-19 situation. This paper observes the issues of teaching theatre at the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic which is shaking up the world. The examination of the issues is focused international tertiary of theatre teaching. However, the paper also offers an investigation of the local context. As it is resumed

after the Spanish flu, the performing-arts institutions definitely resume the practice after COVID-19 pandemic. The practice may not be same as it is now. Physical engagement in theatre class is not possible to imagine as it is prior to COVID-19 pandemic. The interaction between students in the classroom will probably change with the habit of physical and social distancing what people are practicing now.

Methodology :

The paper is presented using a qualitative research method. To explore how the COVID-19 pandemic impacts on theatre in education, the researcher adopts survey method to collect the data. He collects the data from blogs, websites, news and journals. The data is collected based on the areas: online applications, teaching methods, and subject content. Through this data, the researcher draws logical conclusions. Even though it is collected recently, the data rapidly changes day by day. The data is also very huge to synthesize in the selected areas. These two limitations, rapid change of data and huge data, probably effect the research work. To control the limitations, the researcher selected samples randomly across the globe.

Virtual classes and its challenges :

It is already established that many people engage their social life in virtual platform around the world. These online social engagements are observed in most of social networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Skype, WhatsApp, etc. At the end of the 20th century, human-computer interaction theorists observed development of virtual interaction between

people; according to them, “[online platform] is much more a social phenomenon than anything else, with users attracted to the idea that computers are now boxes that connect them with interesting people and exciting places to go, rather than soulless cases that deny social contact” (Dix 1998 156-57). When they are accepting to connect virtually for social engagement, people also probably invite virtual learning. Educators also believe that online teaching engages students very effectively. Satesh Bidaisee expresses that “Teaching an online course can actually be an opportunity to create a more engaging, interactive experience for your students if you take full advantage of the available technology.” (“Inside Higher Ed- Take My Advice” 2017). He also suggests to provide virtual discussion to create “collaborative environment”. Thus, evidences suggest to invite virtual learning.

Nowadays, most of the children from the urban area are rapidly experiencing and adopting technologies. Along with the students, teachers are familiar with digital technology. Anderson observes the importance of teaching theatre in the online platform: “If drama educators cannot or will not find ways to work with technology, students will find other places to express their creativity outside the drama classroom.” (Anderson 2005). When they are capable to adopt the technology, teachers and students create teaching and learning experience in an online platform. In urban India, some students probably allow the online learning easily, but it is very difficult for students of rural India to learn in a virtual classroom. Most of the rural students are not familiar with online classes. Few of them may have a poor internet

connection. Thus, students probably demonstrate inadequate learning experiences in virtual classes.

Along with the technical issues, few of the students distract themselves in virtual learning. During the online classes, instead of virtual learning, some students probably use computers for other activities. For instance, some students, who use computers, possibly spend their time on “social media websites, online shopping, and other personal usage” (Saileela and Kalaivani 79). This distraction is a major challenge to invite online teaching. Consequently, online learning demonstrates both advantage and disadvantages.

When it is compared with English-speaking countries, online learning is not popular in Indian school system. In English-speaking countries, high school children are familiar with remote learning. The theatre subject is explored from “interactive CD-ROMs” websites, and course material. In Indian metro cities, few schools probably have introduced virtual learning many years ago. As the students of English-speaking countries, these metro students possibly demonstrate best learning engagement in virtual platform. This indicates that the large number of students of India are struggling for virtual and remote learning at school level. So, Indian education system needs to adopt online teaching for students.

4. Resolutions to the Challenges :

During this pandemic, most of the corporate schools have invited virtual learning. It is obvious that many teachers got very little time to accept the change in teaching methodology. Few of them were not prepared for this shift, from physical to virtual classroom. When teachers

switched from physical classroom to virtual, many educators needed to alter the syllabus. Few of the educators also shared various resources in social media for online teaching. These resources also digitalized in most cases. The resources include websites for online teaching, video lectures, theatre games, and other teaching tips.

When compare to other subjects, performing arts need a lot of preparation to deliver the content in the virtual platform. This challenge invites a change in theatre syllabus also for virtual learning. For instance, theatre syllabus demands students move in physical space. When it is delivered in virtual platform, theatre syllabus invites many challenges. One of the challenges probably observable in theatre games. In virtual learning, theatre games are not able to play by the students because most of the students wear headphones in the classroom. When they move away from the laptop, students disconnect with the headphones, and they may not follow facilitator instructions. To avoid this miscommunication, some theatre games are suggested to play after providing the guidelines. Once the game is played, the facilitator provides reflection on students' performance. Sometimes, there is a delay in verbal communication between teacher and student in the virtual class; the images are frozen. These issues probably result of a poor network. Because of these issues, students do not engage with theatre games as they do in a physical classroom. Due to these problems, the theatre facilitator must shift from practical to theoretical aspects. This shift is one of the resolutions for virtual theatre teaching. Thus, subject content is needed to alter for virtual theatre classes.

5. Suggested content for virtual Theatre classes :

Three major areas are suitable to teach in online classes. These areas are theatre games; performance based; and theoretical exploration.

a) Theatre games :

When compare to physical classroom, students must be provided more theatre games in virtual classes. In virtual classes, students engage with a computer screen for longtime, so they need to be relaxed in theatre class with theatre games. For this reason, facilitator must provide theatre games to students to engage a lot with the others in the class. Example for these games are "gibberish" (Spolin 123), "funny faceshow" (Rooyackers 99), and "two truths and a lie" (Drama Notebook 2020). Along with these fun-filled games, there are some theatre games for concentration skills. One of these concentration games is listening sounds which is suitable for online classes. In this game, participant is asked to find out the sounds around his place. In this way, selected theatre games are offered for relaxation and concentration.

Apart from fun-filled and concentration games, few storytelling games are suitable for online classes. Storytelling games can be played by one person, and they are suitable for various students from grade 1 to grade 12. "creating a story" is one of the famous theatre games in storytelling category. In this game, each student creates a story based a theme, then he narrates the created story. Some other storytelling games are "one-word story, unfortunately/fortunately, first-liners/last-liners" (Books 2020), "circle story, string tension, word ping pong, and random sound story" (Drama Toolkit - Drama

Games2020). Story telling allows to search into the unknown (Johnstone 75). Sometimes students struggle to tell the story, and the struggle leads to comic situations. As it is always creative and fresh, the storytelling sessions constantly engage the students.

Along with finding suitable theatre games, facilitator needs to provide emotional wellbeing of students. Facilitator requires to create equal opportunity for all the students in theatre games. In many cases, few of the students may mock others. In this case, a teacher needs to discourage participants who mocks others. Students demonstrate positive atmosphere when a teacher offers them to reflect after any activity. For this, teacher invites participants' reflection on the games. Thus, facilitator offers emotional wellbeing to students in virtual platform during theatre games.

b) Performance based :

Facilitator demonstrates many challenges to select performance-oriented exercises for virtual learning. He has to be very specific in selecting a task to teach performance skills because it is difficult to engage many students at a time in the virtual platform. For this, he may select performance tasks designed for a single person to overcome the challenge. These performance tasks are probably organized with various activities such as subtext, mime, emotional memory, solo performance, improvisations, etc. In the performance tasks of signal person, students get the opportunity to express individually. It avoids a lot of communications at a time. Here, when a student is involved with the performance task, others observe and learn.

Exploring subtext is a suitable performance task for a single actor. In this task, the student finds undermined meaning of the dialogue. To perform this, student selects a scene and a character from a script, and he presents undermined meaning of the dialogues. Through this process, he tries to understand dialogues, and demonstrate character with gestures and minimized actions. The extension of the subtext is to create a movement for the character. After exploring the subtext, gestures and minimized actions, the student is asked to present suitable movement of the character in the script. During these performance presentations, other students observe and learn without confusions. Thus, facilitator selects performance tasks at the initial stage of the virtual teaching.

After subtext game, facilitator provides a series of mime activities. In this category, he offers students to present each mime activity for 2 to 3 minutes. As mime activities does not involve dialogues, students avoid speaking at the time of performance. Hence, mime allows visual presentation. For online classes, the best mime activities are pushing a wall, pulling a rope, eating a banana, cleaning an invisible object, and invisible spaces. These activities can be presented by individual participants. In these activities, students do not use any props. They are asked to communicate the specific mime action. The activities engage the students physically and mentally.

Performing a solo theatre performance is also appropriate for virtual class. This task is for both middle and high school students. According the grade level, the duration of the performance can be designed between one to

ten minutes. For this task, first, students are asked to select a character from a play. Then, they will design solo theatre performance based on the character. Along with solo theatre performance, one-man puppet performance engages students well in virtual class. In this task, a student prepare performance with puppets. While solo theatre performance strongly engages middle and high school students, one-man puppet performance deeply involves primary year children. These performances are proposed students to make self-tape. Finally, the facilitator offers his suggestions on the performance. Thus, solo theatre performance and one-man puppet performance gives space for healthy participation in virtual class.

With proper plan, facilitator also selects performance activities for two to four participants for online classes. For example, improvisation is suitable for two to four participants. If they are more than four, participants experience many challenges during improvisations in the virtual learning. Participants enjoy improvisation scenarios of two actors. Many websites provide various scenarios for improvisations (Thrower "Improvisation Scenarios"). From these websites, facilitator selects suitable scenarios for improvisations. Usually, improvisation is key for performance engagement. It offers best "dramatic expression" on the virtual platform. During these improvisations, observers maintain silence. Otherwise, performers get distraction. Thus, facilitator engages students with improvisations in virtual learning.

c) Theoretical exploration :

Most of the students are bored in theoretical exploration, but playwriting does not fall under

this category. Playwriting engages well in virtual learning. With this topic, most of the participants are engaged independently. Playwriting is suggested to start with the basics. Here, students explore Aristotle's dramatic elements: plot, character, diction (speech), thought, spectacle, and song. Gustav Freytag's pyramid theory is also suggested to include in this topic. As part of the analyzing a play, students try to find out the dramatic elements of the Aristotle, analyze five-part model of Freytag's theory. Through this analyzation, students get the opportunity to study the cultural context of the characters. After the exploration of Aristotle's dramatic elements and Freytag's pyramid theory, facilitator introduces a list of the playwriting vocabulary.

Once they are ready with theoretical aspects of playwriting, students are suggested to write a script. Playwriting allows them to engage with imagination, writing, and organizing skills. First, facilitator suggest them to write short plays based on a short story. Later, students write a script based on a theme. In the initial stage, they are advised to follow the structure of playwriting. At this stage, facilitator need to stress on traditional narrative structure. At later stages, students follow their own method of exploration. As it is an individual task, facilitator does not need to monitor students continuously. Students individually write the script. The playwriting task is also advised to give a group of less than five.

Teaching history of theatre allows unnecessary confusions in virtual classes. The course, history of theatre is theoretical and it allows the students to engage independently in virtual learning. As it is an immense area, history

of theatre is not suggested to go in lecture method in virtual platform. In case of long lecture methods, students disconnect with the course. Teaching history of theatre includes knowledge of various genres, directors, playwrights, time periods of theatre. This course offers students to understand ancient to modern theatre. As it is a theoretical subject, facilitator needs to adopt various teaching strategies. To deliver the content, he may depend on power point presentation or video screening. After the delivering the content, worksheets are needed to provide. This allows the students to engage well. It also suggests students to reflect their understanding through drawings and paintings. Here, students write bullet points what they learn, and they draw an image that represents their learning experience. Here, students usually draw the images of scenic design, costumes, props, and stage spaces of various time periods.

After teaching history of theatre, students can explore the director's concepts individually. In this task, students select a play and prepare a director's notebook. Usually, director's notebook is prepared with the details of director's views, ideas, interpretations, production elements and notes for rehearsal process. As part of the director's notebook, students present their interpretation of the play; they design production elements for the play; they understand the character by writing biographies, observing psychological journey, and collecting physical gestures of the characters. In this task, students identify the theme, intention and action of the play. They can also observe "the dramatic action" of the play. Finally, they can prepare rehearsal plan

for the play. This task is suitable for high school children.

Students enjoy another individual task which allows them to write a response to a performance. The task allows the students to work independently. For this task, students are provided a theatre performance which is available online. After watching the play, students are asked to write a response. Depends on the grade, they are guided to write the reflection. These guidelines are broad to specific: elements of theatre to specific topic. For high school, students are suggested to write the function of theatrical elements in the performance. In case of primary and middle year program, students are recommended to write how a specific topic drives the performance. These specific topics are derived from the elements of theatre: physical and voice acting; costumes, props, stage design, make-up, lighting, stage design and sound; plot, dialogues and locations. According to their grade, students are expected to write between 2 lines to 250 words. Through this task, each student uniquely presents individual responses to selected topic.

Students also enjoy quiz for once in a week. After delivering theoretical aspects of theatre, subject knowledge is advised to assess with one of the assessment tools, quiz. Quiz is recommended with 15 to 25 questions. Each quiz requires to organize with a suitable online application. The suggested applications for quiz are "Kahoot, Google Classroom, Quizlet, BookWidgets, Seesaw, Poll Everywhere, Aurasma, Photomath, and Explain Everything" (Renard 2017). The quiz can be organized with a single student or partners. For

best learning process, student is strongly recommended to work with partners.

6. Facilitator's role in virtual classes :

Usually a theatre teacher facilitates various projects, process of the performances and activities in the classroom. Instead of calling him as theatre teacher, most of the organizations refer him as theatre facilitator. A facilitator or teacher must be trained properly to teach in a virtual platform. A teacher is suggested to familiar with various online teaching tools. Before he starts a class, a teacher must create essential agreements to avoid unnecessary communication during the virtual lessons. As part of the essential agreements, teacher needs to communicate to student to mute the microphones once they login virtual classes. They unmute the microphones when students want to speak. Students are asked to turn the camera on during the class, so that teacher can monitor them. To engage students well, the teacher needs to introduce documents in various forms: websites, audio, video, pictures, graphs, and live chats. He always requires to invite students to explain keywords, ask questions, and give short seminars. These activities allow students to engage lively.

In case of theatre class, students are strongly suggested to have an empty room to do the activities. After giving a task in classroom, facilitator make sure that students finish on time. Sometimes they spend a lot of time for discussions. Sometimes they may take the wrong approach for the task. For instance, students spend a lot of time during the improvisations. For another example, in creating a script, some students may take much time. In this case, facilitator needs to help them to finish

the task on right time. When they are working with the groups, some students may not allow others to share their reflection. In such situations, facilitator make sure that everybody gets an equal opportunity in the participation. For this, he must use grouping strategy.

Some theatre tasks demand grouping strategy. Usually, grouping allows students to work with various people. The grouping is also influence students' learning, and it offers collaboration, communication, teamwork, and active participation. In many situations, students show interest to form a group with their friends. Facilitator may allow them initially, but later stages he avoids them to work with their friends. Thus, grouping plays a significant role in virtual learning.

During virtual classes, theatre facilitator is accountable to create an opportunity for students to engage with learning objects. Like the physical class, virtual class is expressive when participants are engaged with two-way interaction between teacher and students. Accepting all the technical glitches, the facilitator must be concerned with dynamic engagement in virtual class. To create the dynamic class engagement and the two-way interaction, theatre facilitator needs to design course with textual, peer-to-peer, participant-to-facilitator engagement.

7. Online Platforms :

As they are being isolated at home, students are not allowed to attend public places such as schools and parks, and to see visitors. Students are being in isolation leads to stress. Government and psychologists suggested the parents to monitor their children. Parents are guided to allow the students to keep in touch

with friends via social media, telecommunication or emails. To interact with others in the virtual world, people are using few other online platforms such as Zoom, Google Hangouts, Google Meet, Houseparty, Skype, Microsoft Teams, Facetime, Cisco Webex, Starleaf, Whereby, Slack, Gotomeeting, BlueJeans, Appair.in, BigBlueButton and many more. Educational institutes are adopting some of these online platforms for virtual classes. With these platforms, students get the opportunity to interact, discuss and practice with others. There are few apps that are suggested for virtual classes, and they are Zoom, Socrative, Evernote, Edmodo, Doceri, Instructables, TeacherKit Educreations, StudyBlue, Kahoot, Additio, Classtree, Dropbox, Groovy Grader, Seesaw, Pocket, Teacher's Assistant Pro, WolframAlpha, ClassDojo, Trello, Google Classroom, Slack, Remind, TED and Eco360. The online platforms partially fulfil the classroom needs, and the challenges of virtual classroom are unsolved.

a) Zoom :

Many educators prefer Zoom for their virtual teaching. It provides secure virtual communication for less than 100 students. This online application offers unlimited service for free. The Zoom users have access to “unlimited meeting for up to 100 participants; HD audio and video; Screen sharing; White boarding; Annotation; Breakout rooms; Virtual backgrounds; In-meeting chat; Local recording; and Nonverbal feedback”(Zoom Is Now Free for K-12 Schools). To use the application, one must sign up with school email; the application allows personal domains such as “Gmail AOL Outlook ZohoMail.com Yahoo! Mail Proton

Mail iCloud Mail GMX Mail Mozilla Thunderbird Yandex Mail” (The 9 Best Free Email Accounts and Service Providers for 2020). If any educational organization wants to use the app, the administrator needs to fill an online verification form. Then, the form will be processed and verified by Zoom. Finally, administrator receives the message to start Zooming. Initially, the time limit was 40 min, now it is fixed to unlimited. When the administrator increases the limit of participants for 300, Zoom charges low cost. For best experience, Zoom users are suggested to mute the microphones when they are not talking, and chat to raise a question.

b) Google :

Google also provides few applications for online teaching. These applications project most features as Zoom does. From the Google family, there are three popular applications available for virtual classroom. They are Google Hangouts, Google Classroom, and Google Meets. While Google Meets and Google Hangouts provide video conference, Google Classroom does not provide video conference. Google Hangouts and Google Meets, along with video conference, allow to share images, instant messages, computer screen, and documents.

To organize paperless documents, Google Classroom is best application. It allows to create, distribute, and assess the tasks in digital format. While Google Hangouts and Google Meets are designed for various people, Google Classroom is developed for classroom learning. In Google Classroom, a teacher can post documents to a specific class. He communicates through Gmail to post feedback or announcements. He can add or delete students from the

Google Application. Along with these three, a teacher can use few other applications from Google family. They are Google Docs, Google Sheets, Google Calendar, and Google Drive and Google Slides. These applications are designed to organize various documents. Google Docs is well designed to write reports and share content. Google Sheets intended to organize the data in table format. Google Slides is best for presentations. Google Calendar is good to remind the due date of a task. Finally, Google Drive can be used to store any file for online use. Applications from google family can be regulated with a code to specific person; they are well designed to work on a specific document online by one or more people. These applications are also designed for Android and iOS mobile phones.

8. Skills for teacher to organize virtual class :

It is obvious that a teacher must have listening skills. When compare to physical classroom, virtual classroom demands a teacher with best listening skills. In a virtual classroom, he has to be an expert to adopt a vast range of teaching strategies. Teacher needs to be empathetic; it allows best connection between students and teacher. Teacher must provide a space for students to ask a question. He must respond properly. This allows students to be good inquirers. In case of virtual class, students post questions in chat box. Teacher must have an eye on the chat box to answer those questions. In few occasions, some students post unnecessary messages. Teacher must politely discourage such activities. Teacher has to be reasonable in giving formative assignments, home works, task sheets and assignments.

Teacher must follow micro plan with clear expectations. Teacher needs to accept submission of any task after due date. This flexibility allows students to gain benefits. After submission of any task by student, a teacher is suggested to provide appropriate feedback. The feedback allows the students to reach the subject expectations.

9. Requirements for online lessons :

First thing is accessibility of a computer and built-in camera; earphones or headphone; and internet. This allows a student to connect with a facilitator and with his peers. If they are offered wireless Bluetooth headphones and microphone, students get opportunity move freely for given activity. Facilitator keeps his space wide enough to demonstrate activities. He always tries to be visible to the students. At the same time, he proposes students to be visible in the screen for the best class. Facilitator and students require to make essential agreements for the virtual class. Encourage the students who follows essential agreements. Facilitator has to be ready for technical glitches. In such situations, he needs to adopt the situation and deliver the content. In few cases, some students may not have computer or internet. For them, he has to have alternative plans.

Second thing is selecting online application what can be accessed by both facilitator and students. Both parties, students and facilitator, need to install a selected application in their respective computers. Then, facilitator needs to be ready with video, audio and textual files. In case of video files, the facilitator has to be ready with a specific video format, so that students can access easily. If it is an online video source, facilitator needs to check the video

quality. The facilitator is suggested to save the files to the Googlecloud before he gets in the virtual class. The facilitator needs to give permission to students to access the Google cloud. He requires creating a folder for each student, so a student can submit his work in this folder. Shared Google cloud and the folders save the facilitator answering the following questions frequently. These questions: where can I access a specific file? how can I submit my work? and how can I see your reflection on my work? The facilitator needs to remind the students to watch for and reply to messages from him as early as possible. Facilitator must be passionate in fulfilling students' expectations. Facilitator must be a good communicator, and he needs to share his syllabus to the students.

10. Privacy Protection :

Educational institutes must commit to protect students' privacy when they switch to virtual classes. In several countries, laws control the use of internet in schools. For example, *Children's Online Privacy Protection Act* (COPPA, Pub. L. No. 105-277) guards the students' privacy under age 13 (*CHILDREN'S ONLINE PRIVACY PROTECTION*). According to COPPA, websites which engage students under age 13 essential follow necessary procedures to deal with students' personal data. To provide child's safety, the school must monitor the online accounts of the students and the teachers. For this, most of the institutes maintain students' and teachers' account with "G suite for education" (G Suite for Education | Google for Education). This allows them to protect their privacy.

11. Remote learning :

In India, the most of the students cannot afford internet access and computer. The government of India needs to provide alternative learning for the students who do not have access to internet and computers. The government needs to support these students providing textbooks, workbooks, articles, notebooks, etc. These students must be guided with few activities: reading a book for 40 minutes per a day; practicing workbook for 40 minutes per a day; writing a reflection on a specific topic per a day; and drawing mind maps, clip-art and flow charts on their understanding of a specific topic. For theatre subject, these students can be asked to explore the history of theatre, write a script, design production elements, and respond to a specific theatre form. It is not possible to organize theatre games for these students. Contrast to these students, the other group of students, who studies in corporate schools, can afford computers and internet. This group of children can be part of theatre class with limited theatre games and theory.

12. Conclusion :

It is obviously too early to conclude virtual learning in Covid-19 pandemic. Many teachers are adopting many applications for online teaching. Every day a new application is introduced in the market. Various teachers across the globe use various applications and various teaching methods to teach in a virtual platform. When I look at the data, I know that I scratched a bit on the field, still need to find a lot in this topic. This study analyzed the various contents and methods that are suitable for online teaching. It also presented evidences of challenges in the virtual teaching. the resolution of these

challenges suggested alternative methods in taught curriculum. To resolve these problems, the teacher was creative and imaginative to alter the curriculum. This research is synthesized with teaching methods for theatre teachers to deliver the subject in online teaching.

Bibliography :

1. Renard. "20 Fun Apps to Put Your Students' Smartphones to Good Use." BookWidgets Blog, 17 May 2017, www.bookwidgets.com/blog/2017/05/20-fun-apps-to-put-your-students-smartphones-to-good-use.
2. [USC02] 15 USC Ch. 91: CHILDREN'S ONLINE PRIVACY PROTECTION, uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?path=/prelim@title15/chapter91&edition=prelim.
3. Anderson, Michael. "New Stages: Challenges for Teaching the Aesthetics of Drama Online." *The Journal of Aesthetic Education*, vol. 39, no. 4, 2005, pp. 119–131., doi:10.1353/jae.2005.0035.
4. Becker, Braden. "The 9 Best Free Email Accounts and Service Providers for 2020." HubSpot Blog, blog.hubspot.com/marketing/free-email-accounts.
5. Books, Drama Start. "Storytelling Games." Drama Start, 17 May 2020, dramastartbooks.com/2012/12/27/storytelling-games/.
6. Dix, Alan J. *Human-Computer Interaction*. Prentice Hall Europe, 1998.
7. Drama Notebook. "Two Truths and a Lie Drama Game." Drama Notebook, DramaNotebook, 30 Apr. 2020, www.dramanotebook.com/drama-games/two-truths-and-a-lie/.
8. Saileela, and Kalaivani. *Education on Digital Cultural and Social Media*. Lulu.com, 2019.
9. "G Suite for Education | Google for Education." Google, Google, edu.google.com/products/gsuite-for-education/?modal_active=none.
10. Thrower. "Improvisation Scenarios." Stuff, cloudcuckoo.co.uk/jonthrower/improv_scen.htm.
11. "Inside Higher Ed-Take My Advice." Peer Advice for Instructors Teaching Online for First Time, 15 Nov. 2017, www.insidehighered.com/digital-learning/article/2017/11/15/peer-advice-instructors-teaching-online-first-time.
12. Johnstone, Keith. *Impro for Storytellers*. Faber and Faber, 1999.
13. "Plot." Drama Toolkit - Drama Games - Plot, 21 Sept. 2020, www.dramatoolkit.co.uk/drama-games/category/plot.
14. Rooyackers, Paul. *101 Drama Games for Children: Fun and Learning with Acting and Make-Believe*. Hunter House Inc., Publishers, 1998.
15. Spolin, Viola. *Theater Games for the Classroom: a Teachers Handbook*. Northwestern Univ. Press, 2000.
16. "Zoom Is Now Free for K-12 Schools! What You Need To Know." *DGI Communications*, 13 Aug. 2020, www.dgicomunications.com/zoom-is-now-free-for-k-12-schools-what-you-and-your-students-need-to-know/.

